

**EPIDEMIOLOGICAL PROFILE OF VIRAL HEPATITIS CASES IN
THE MUNICIPALITY OF CAXIAS MARANHÃO: FROM 2017 TO 2022**

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ABSTRACT

Viral hepatitis represents a serious public health problem due to its high prevalence, incidence and mortality. Hepatitis caused by hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV) and

hepatitis D virus (HDV), are transmitted parenterally, are not highly contagious, and are capable of leading to the development of chronic disease. The objective of the present study was to analyze and describe the epidemiological profile of cases of hepatitis reported from 2017 to 2022 in the city of Caxias Maranhão and to contribute with knowledge on the subject. It was a descriptive research with a quantitative approach on the reported cases of viral hepatitis in the Caxias State scenario, totaling 41 reported cases. The data show that, over the years, notifications of hepatitis cases in the city of Caxias have been reduced. The highest number of cases was observed in 2017 (34.1%) and the lowest number in 2021 (0%). Among Viral Hepatitis, hepatitis B had a higher occurrence, with a frequency of 46.6%. The relevance of creating more studies on this topic is concluded, focusing on the incidence and underreporting of viral hepatitis cases to help the epidemiological surveillance authorities to develop actions in order to make health professionals aware of the importance of case notification.

Keywords: Viral hepatitis; Epidemiology; public health.

INTRODUCTION

From 1999 to 2018, in Brazil, 632,814 cases were reported according to the Notification Information System (SINAN) (BRASIL, 2019). Viral hepatitis represents a serious public health problem due to its high prevalence, incidence and mortality rates. For this reason, cases of hepatitis are considered “notifiable” cases. Compulsory notification is defined as the mandatory communication of information to the competent health authorities, which must be carried out by a doctor, health professional or head of a public or private institution, in case of suspected or confirmed disease, which can be immediate or weekly (TIMÓTEO *et al* .,2020).

Viral hepatitis is a disease caused by different pathogens that commonly share a hepatotropic nature. The importance of hepatitis is not limited to a large number of people already infected; it also extends to acute and chronic complications. The cause of hepatitis determines a wide range of clinical manifestations, from asymptomatic carriers to acute or chronic hepatitis. In the last decades, the work of prevention and control of hepatitis achieved remarkable results, due to the improvement of hygiene conditions and vaccination against hepatitis (FERREIRA ; SILVEIRA , 2004).

Hepatitis caused by hepatitis B (VHB), C (HCV) and D (HDV) viruses are transmitted parenterally, are not highly contagious, rarely cause outbreaks and are capable of leading to the development of chronic diseases and evolutionary complications, especially cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). It also has the possibility of systemic involvement, as in the case of infection by HBV, implying the development of polyarteritis, glomerulonephritis, polymyalgia rheumatica, cryoglobulinemia, etc. (DA SILVA, 2012) .

Therefore, the objective of the present study was to analyze and describe the epidemiological profile of cases of viral hepatitis reported in the period from 2017 to 2022 in the municipality of Caxias Maranhão. Thus providing essential data for the planning, execution and evaluation of prevention, control and treatment of viral hepatitis.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Epidemiology of viral hepatitis

Viral hepatitis (VH) are systemic infectious diseases with tropism for the liver tissue, which have important differences between themselves and regional particularities, being a serious public health problem in Brazil and in the world, since they generate broad impacts of morbidity and mortality by causing a inflammation in the liver and because they have the ability to progress to chronic disease. In Brazil, the main circulating serotypes are viruses A, B, C and D, which cause diseases that present with distinct epidemiological and clinical characteristics (BANDEIRA, 2018).

Between 2010 and 2020, there were 388,188 cases of viral hepatitis in Brazil, with a predominance of Hepatitis C infections, which were responsible for 189,001 cases (48.69%), followed by Hepatitis B infections, which were responsible by 153,304 cases (39.49%). An increase in the incidence of viral hepatitis was observed, from 16.33 in 2010 to 16.87 in 2019, with a peak of 21.26 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in 2015. However, there was an abrupt drop in the incidence in 2020, which increased to 7.47, due to probable underreporting of cases, resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. (MATOS; ZÖLLNER , 2022)

Viral hepatitis in the Maranhão scenario

According to Sousa (2021), from 2010 to 2018, 41,209 cases of viral hepatitis (11.92%) were reported in the Northeast. In the ranking of number of infections, among all states, the Northeast ranks fourth. It was noted that hepatitis B had the highest concentration (33.9%), followed by type C virus (32.3%) and type A virus (28.7%), and 5.1% inconclusive by the research. Most cases were male, brown, with high school education.

In relation to the state of Maranhão, in the period from 2016 to 2020, it was found that the year with the highest percentages of infection was the year 2018 with 451 confirmed cases (29.32%), while the year 2020 concentrated lower percentages, 126 cases (8.19%). It was found that the profile of individuals most affected by viral hepatitis was female, adults between 20

and 49 years old, brown and with high school education, with sexual intercourse being the predominant means of transmission (FERREIRA ; DURANS , 2022) .

Management of viral hepatitis in public services

Despite the new SUS ordering system, including the provision of health services such as vaccination, serological tests, among others, diseases such as viral hepatitis continue to be a challenge for health, because when they are not diagnosed and treated properly, they can evolve into forms serious compromising the liver, causing advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis, which can lead to the development of cancer and the need for organ transplantation (BRASIL, 2020).

1. The treatment it differs according to the serotype for the disease. Hepatitis A and E do not have a specific treatment. The most important thing is to avoid self-medication to relieve symptoms, since the use of unnecessary medications or those that are toxic to the liver can worsen the condition. Regarding hepatitis B, there is no cure for it. However, the treatment available in the SUS aims to reduce the risk of disease progression and its complications, specifically cirrhosis, liver cancer and death. The drugs available to control this condition are peginterferon alfa, tenofovir and entecavir (SESA, 2020).

2. Hepatitis C treatment is done with so-called direct-acting antivirals (DAA), which have cure rates of over 95% and are usually performed for 8 or 12 weeks. All people infected with the hepatitis C virus (HCV) can receive treatment through the SUS. Patients in the initial phase of the infection can be treated in basic health units, without the need for consultation in the specialized network to initiate treatment. Now, for hepatitis D, patients must undergo therapies, they are composed of peginterferon alfa and/or a nucleoside analogue, all available by SUS (BRASIL, 2005).

Screening for viral hepatitis

Because it causes thousands of deaths and chronic liver problems, screening for viral hepatitis is very important. Diseases can be controlled with early diagnosis, treatment and preventive measures, including vaccines for some types of the virus. One of the major problems in diagnosing viral hepatitis is that many people do not feel anything in the initial phase of the infection. Especially in cases of hepatitis B and C, as symptoms usually only appear when the disease is advanced. Therefore, it is important to take the test, which is available free of charge in basic health units (FIOCRUZ, 2021).

Regardless of the strategy for using the rapid test, it is important that even in campaign environments, a suitable place is reserved for the reception of individuals, as well as for carrying out counseling with adequate privacy for those who have reactive results, if the user so wish. In addition to the speed of the result, the opportunities for offering and carrying out the test can be established according to the routine of each service, which may occur in screening for appointments, nursing appointments, medical appointments, home visits and even in groups of patients or services performed by other health professionals (BRASIL, 2005).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive retrospective research with a quantitative approach, on reported cases of viral hepatitis in the Caxias do Sul scenario.

The research area was carried out in Caxias, a municipality in the state of Maranhão, in the Mid-North region of Brazil. It is the fifth most populous city in the state, with a population of 166,159 inhabitants, according to IBGE data for 2021 (figure 1).

Figure 1- map of the city of Caxias (MA)

Source: caxiasmaranhaoma.blogspot, 2022.

The population was defined by the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis infections carried out by health services in the city of Caxias-MA from January 2017 to May 2022, totaling 41 reported cases . The Municipal Health Department of the municipality was asked to provide data on viral hepatitis for the epidemiological surveillance service regarding the variables: year, age, sex, education, occupation, whether they had been vaccinated for hepatitis A and/or B, clinical form , etiological classification, and the probable source/mechanism of infection.

After receiving the data, the *software* Epi Info version 7.2 was used for the statistical survey, which was used to assemble the database, to enter the information, to process the data and for the statistical analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

From 2017 to 2022, 41 new cases of viral hepatitis for all clinical forms were reported in Caxias-MA. The representation of the number of cases per year is shown in Graph 1.

Graph 1- Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, by year of notification, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

The data indicate that, over the years, the notifications of cases of hepatitis in the city of Caxias have been reduced. Research claims that notifications of hepatitis cases in Brazil have also been reduced (TIMÓTEO *et al* ,2020). The highest number of cases was observed in 2017 (34.1%) and the lowest number in 2021 (0%) (Graph 1). The reduction in the number of case notifications in 2020 and 2021 may be related to underreporting due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly interferes with the results (ARAÚJO, 2017).

In order to analyze the profile of infected patients in this period, some variables were used, such as the one shown in Graph 2, representing patients by gender.

Graph 2 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral Hepatitis, by sex in a patient in the city of Caxias Maranhão in each year, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

The percentages of cases of viral hepatitis by gender in each year show that in 2017 and 2018, female and male notifications were equal (50%), while in the following year (2019) a change in the epidemiological pattern is highlighted. , regarding gender, of viral hepatitis, notification of male cases were higher, totaling 75% of notifications. In 2020, 100% of the cases reported that year were female.

In the year 2021, no cases were reported, and in the year 2022, until the month of May, the highest number of notifications was male (62.5%) (Graph 2). Because, according to authors, many of them are not concerned with health care, such as attending medical appointments and adopting preventive measures. Due to the lack of self-care, men end up becoming more vulnerable/exposed to diseases due to their lifestyle (MOURA, GOMES, PEREIRA, 2017).

To represent the most common clinical form of hepatitis, the distribution of the number of notified cases was made, as shown in Graph 3.

Graph 3 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, by clinical form, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

Chronic hepatitis (51.2%) was identified as the main clinical form of notified cases of hepatitis in the city of Caxias, knowing that the three types of viral hepatitis B, C and D can cause chronic hepatitis and that they only differ in its mode of transmission, evolution and prognosis. It can be defined for a period longer than 6 months after an Acute Hepatitis. The other most frequent clinical form is acute hepatitis (19.5%) (Graph 3). Which represents the scenario of hepatitis in Brazil well: chronic hepatitis (77%) and acute hepatitis (13%) (TIMÓTEO *et al.*, 2020).

Regarding the etiological classification, the representation of the notified cases was made as shown in Graph 4.

Graph 4 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, by etiological classification, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

Considering that many infected individuals are asymptomatic and that symptomatic infections are insufficiently notified, the frequency of hepatitis B was 46.3%. Among the Viral Hepatitis, hepatitis B had a higher occurrence. This stands out as a serious public health problem in the world. Hepatitis C is the second most frequent with 29.2% (Graph 4), there is no vaccine for hepatitis C. It is believed that this may be one of the main factors that may be related to the large number of infections by subtype C.

To demonstrate the percentage of vaccination for cases of viral hepatitis, the distribution of reported data was made, as shown in Graph 5.

Graph 5 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, by vaccination, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

Viruses A, B, and C are responsible for the vast majority of acute forms of the infection. Virus A is the most common cause of acute viral hepatitis. We have vaccines against hepatitis A, both live, attenuated and inactivated viruses, the vaccines are highly immunogenic and safe, producing 95% to 100% of serum conversion in healthy individuals. Vaccination against HBV is the most effective way to prevent acute or chronic infection and to eliminate virus transmission in all age groups (FERREIRA ; SILVEIRA , 2004).

It can be seen (Graph 5) that 68.2% of those infected had not been vaccinated against hepatitis type A, and 48.7% against hepatitis B. An aggravating factor for the evolution of the case to the chronic form. Only 12.2% of people had completed hepatitis B vaccination.

In order to show the number of pregnant women with hepatitis, the number of cases was divided into percentages, as shown in Graph 6.

Graph 6 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, in pregnant women, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

The hepatitis virus can produce transplacental infections, determining fetal hepatitis responsible for neonatal jaundice (LEFÈVRE, 1971). The importance of vaccination and carrying out prenatal care for pregnant women is given. According to data from the current study (Graph 6), in 2017 and 2018, 11.1% of cases were in pregnant women, in 2019 no cases were reported in pregnant women and in 2020, 5.5% of reported cases were in pregnant women.

Graph 7 shows the distribution of confirmed cases of hepatitis by age group in the city under analysis in this study.

Graph 7 - Number of confirmed cases of viral hepatitis, by age group, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

Although the studied population is heterogeneous, the occurrence was more frequent in the age group of 36-45 years (34.1%) and 46-55 years (19.5%). Followed by the 15-25 age group (17%) and the over 65 age group (12.2%). As shown in the present sample (Graph 7), there is no high prevalence of the number of cases in adolescence, a fact that stems from the profile of the population treated at the hospital, which is mostly adult patients.

To divide the cases of hepatitis according to the sources of infection, data analysis was performed as shown in Graph 8.

Graph 8 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, by probable source/mechanism of infection, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

Of the most frequently reported forms of transmission (Graph 8) throughout the study period, sexual transmission (21.9%) predominated, which reveals low adherence to condom use during sexual intercourse, suggesting that this is one of the factors that most risk for acquiring hepatitis since sexual transmission is typical of moderately endemic regions (SILVA, 2015).

Infection by other mechanisms was 12.2%, by contaminated food/water represented 4.8% , this result can also be associated with the most frequent type of virus, since water and food contaminated with feces with virus A are the great vehicles for the spread of the disease, therefore, the water used and the hygiene of the food have great relevance in the occurrence of the disease (VIEIRA *et al* ,.2010). Furthermore, 48.7% of notifications left this part of the epidemiological form blank or ignored.

With regard to the occupation of people notified with hepatitis, the distribution was made as shown in Graph 8.

Graph 9 - Distribution of the number of notified cases of viral hepatitis, by occupation, in the city of Caxias Maranhão, from 2017 to May 2022.

Source: Sinan - Epidemiological Surveillance of the Municipal Health Department, Caxias - MA, 2022.

The data indicate that among those infected, 29.2% were housewives, farmers and retirees, both representing 17%, 7.3% pedal vehicle drivers, 4.8% were commercial workers, 4.8% students and 2.4% % were concrete structure builders, mechanics, welders and teachers. Given the analysis (Graph 9), it is possible to see that the highest percentage is in people who have less education, as a result of this, they do not have guidance about what hepatitis is and especially its forms of transmission and prevention. Thus, a failure in the health system is notorious, and there needs to be a correction and organization of the means used to distribute information about this to the less educated population.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Through the present study, it was possible to trace the epidemiological profile of viral hepatitis in the municipality of Caxias Maranhão, where 41 cases were studied from 2017 to May 2022.

The cases studied, with the largest number in 2017, registered a decrease in notifications of hepatitis cases over the years, reaching the point of not registering any cases in 2021. It is clear that the impact of the pandemic on the health issue caused problems in the identification and underreporting of other diseases. The isolation of people, the lack of correct knowledge about the disease and its symptoms, and a very high number of deaths to be underreported

during the pandemic, resulted in a decrease in people working, with many errors and lack of data reported on other diseases.

As demonstrated within this study, the results showed that there was no significant discrepancy between males and females. Chronic hepatitis is the main clinical form found, in relation to the etiological classification, the one that prevailed was the B virus. Among those infected, the highest percentage belongs to housewives and the most frequent occurrence is in the age group of 36-45 years.

Thus, it is concluded that it is extremely important to create more studies on this topic, focusing on the incidence and underreporting of cases of viral hepatitis, to help epidemiological surveillance authorities to develop actions to make health professionals aware of the importance notification of cases, as well as information on prevention, diagnosis and control of the disease with a view to breaking the chain of transmission.

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